

Diabetes Awareness, Perceived Complications, and Prevention Practices among Rural Dwellers in Selected Parts of Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Diabetes mellitus is a growing serious public health challenge, especially in low and middle-income nations where knowledge and management of the condition remains poor. The current study aimed at evaluating awareness about risk factors, symptoms, preventive methods, complications of diabetes and public knowledge about the illness among rural residents of Owerri West and Owerri North LGAs of Imo State. A descriptive cross sectional survey design was applied among 1,200 respondents randomly selected from six rural communities of Owerri North and Owerri West LGAs via a multistage sampling procedure. Questionnaire data collection tool was employed in gathering information that was analyzed statistically using frequency distribution table. The prevalence rate for diabetes was 15.0% compared to previous figures found nationally in Nigeria. Type-2 diabetes constituted 66.7% of the diagnosed diabetes cases while 11.1% of the study participants did not know their types of diabetes. Moderate levels of overall knowledge were recorded for diabetes with 41.7% having poor, 33.3% fair and 25.0% good levels of diabetes knowledge. Risk factors were known by most of the respondents; family history (66.7%), obesity (58.3%), unhealthy diet (50.0%), alcohol (41.7%) and cigarette smoking (37.5%). Frequent urination (66.7%), excessive thirst (62.5%) and fatigue (58.3%) were the well-known diabetes symptoms. Exercise, healthy eating habits, and maintaining body weight were cited by most of the participants (75.0%, 70.8%, and 66.7%, respectively), as important preventive strategies. Participants' knowledge about serious complications such as heart diseases, kidney diseases, and vision loss (70.8%, 66.7%, and 62.5%, respectively) was found to be relatively good. However, poor knowledge about complications such as sexual dysfunction and dental problems was noted. Thus, based on this study, there is a clear indication that while the level of knowledge about diabetes is relatively satisfactory, there are still notable knowledge gaps.

Keywords: *Diabetes mellitus; awareness; complications; prevention; rural communities; public health; Imo State; Nigeria.*

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is an incurable metabolic condition marked by the presence of persistently elevated blood sugar levels as a result of impaired insulin secretion or its effectiveness or both. This disease is considered to be one of the most prevalent non-communicable conditions worldwide, posing serious health threats into the twenty-first century (Standl *et al.*, 2019; Saeedi *et al.*, 2019; Cho *et al.*, 2018). As per the reports of the International Diabetes Federation, nearly 537 million individuals worldwide had diabetes in 2021, whereas it would amount to 643 million and 783 million by 2030 and

2045, respectively. The incidence of diabetes is increasing at an alarming pace within Sub-Saharan Africa, especially within Nigeria, due to factors like urbanization, poor dietary practices, physical inactivity, and changes within lifestyle (WHO, 2022). DM is responsible for contributing to disability, mortality rate, and increased medical expenses worldwide. In Type 1 DM, there is destruction of beta cells present within pancreas, while in Type 2 DM, responsible for up to 95% of the diabetes cases across the world, the presence of insulin resistance has been established (Banday *et al.*, 2020; Xu *et al.*, 2018; Tao *et al.*, 2015). Untreated cases

of DM lead to various complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular diseases, and diabetic foot ulcers, which greatly reduce quality of life and may result in death (Waheedi *et al.*, 2017).

It has been found that the success of diabetes management is dependent on the patients' knowledge, attitudes, adherence, and self-care behaviors (Anderson *et al.*, 2020; Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2015; Eldarrat, 2011; Gul, 2010). Effective diabetes management involves adherence to medications, living a healthy lifestyle, and proper medical attention (Lin *et al.*, 2012; Hermanns *et al.*, 2010; Peyrot *et al.*, 2005; Clark, 2004). It has been observed that there is an increased prevalence of diabetes in Nigeria, ranging between 3%-10%. There is poor awareness among people regarding diabetes, and due to lack of early diagnosis and management, the condition poses a significant problem (WHO, 2022; Chijioke *et al.*, 2010). It should be noted that rural areas are highly susceptible to diabetes, owing to poor healthcare facilities, lack of qualified healthcare professionals, lack of health literacy among people, poverty, and dependence on traditional medicines (Anderson *et al.*, 2020). Lack of awareness and poor availability of diagnostic facilities lead to the high number of people with untreated or unmanaged diabetes in rural communities (Waheedi *et al.*, 2017). Poor awareness leads to high morbidity and mortality rates in rural communities owing to poor management and prevention practices (Ajayi and Ajayi, 2009; Chijioke *et al.*, 2010). Diabetes control and prevention are achieved through behavioral changes and proper medical care (American Diabetes Association, 2013).

Proper diet, regular exercise, weight control, and drug compliance are necessary in preventing the occurrence of complications and improving their standard of living. There have been studies that showed people with high knowledge about the condition tend to practice self-care measures and suffer less from complications of the disease (Waheedi *et al.*, 2017; Chavan *et al.*, 2015). Thus, diabetes education and self-management are highly recommended according to both national and international guidelines (Powers *et al.*, 2015). In this case, the study will focus on the rural community within Owerri West and Owerri North LGAs, Imo State, Nigeria. Despite being close to the state capital, many people residing in the rural areas have little or no access to modern healthcare facilities, hence relying on herbal medications, spiritual healing centers, and traditional medicine when dealing with chronic conditions like diabetes. Poor knowledge of diabetes, lack of access to proper healthcare facilities, and low awareness levels lead to late diagnosis and occurrence of complicated cases among rural people. Therefore, a study of awareness, complications, and preventive strategies regarding diabetes in the rural population is important.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross sectional survey study was conducted in Six (6) communities purposively selected from Owerri West and Owerri North Local Government Areas of Imo State between January 2025 and February, 2026. Owerri West is located between latitude 4°0'14' N and 6°0'15' N, and longitude 6°0'51' E while Owerri North is located between latitude 5°27'24.26' N and longitude 7°06'9.83' E. Owerri West and Owerri North are two out of the 27 Local Government Areas in Imo State with its headquarters at Umuguma and Orié Uratta, respectively. Owerri West and Owerri North LGAs are characterized by a mix of peri-urban and predominantly rural communities, which makes them highly suitable for a study focused on rural health issues such as diabetes and its complications. Given the socioeconomic, environmental, cultural, and healthcare characteristics of Owerri West and Owerri North LGAs, these areas provide a relevant context for studying diabetes and its complications among rural dwellers. The combination of poor health infrastructure, limited disease awareness, traditional beliefs, and low-income levels presents a challenging but vital landscape for understanding the burden of diabetes in underserved populations. This study was approved by the Postgraduate Board of Imo State University, Owerri and permission was obtained from Imo State Ministry of Health Unit. Informed consent (written) was also obtained from the Traditional Rulers (Ezes and Heads of communities) in the study areas and thereafter, oral consents were obtained from the study participants. Advocacy visit was conducted to facilitate community engagement for a study investigating diabetes prevalence, complications, and management practices among rural populations. The study population comprised all adults from the Six (6) communities under study (Okuku, Amakohia-Ubi, Ndegwu from Owerri West LGA, while Emii, Obibiezena and Emekuku from Owerri North LGA). The communities were randomly selected from two Local Government Areas in Owerri Zone of Imo State. The subjects' educational qualification, occupation, gender, marital status, religion, etc were put into consideration.

The total sample size for the study was 1,200 participants; Two hundred (200) from each of the study areas. The sample size of 1,200 participants was derived from the table below for a minimum sample size estimate for a population survey with 95% confidence interval using Lemeshow *et al* (1990) formula. To assess diabetes awareness, complications, and preventive practices among rural dwellers, the approaches used by Kassa (2021) and Al-Maskari (2013) were adopted. A structured questionnaire covering demographics, knowledge of symptoms, complications, and prevention was administered in both English and the local language (Bintabara *et al.*, 2017). To enrich the data, focus group

discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs) with health workers and community leaders explored perceptions and contextual factors (Choudhury *et al.*, 2014; Beran *et al.*, 2016). Data collection involved face-to-face interviews and observations during community health events (Puoane *et al.*, 2005).

RESULTS:

From 1,200 participants (Table 1), 180 (15.0%) were reported to have been diagnosed with diabetes; Obibi-Ezena was observed to have the highest prevalence (18.0%) while Emekuku recorded the lowest prevalence (10.5%). Amongst those diagnosed with diabetes, 66.7% of them had Type-2 diabetes while 16.7% of them had Type-1 diabetes; 11.1% did not know the types of diabetes they had. Majority of the respondents (44.4%) have had diabetes for 1-5 years while 11.1% had the disease for more than 10 years. Knowledge level evaluation found that 41.7% of them have poor knowledge on diabetes, 33.3% had fair knowledge while 25.0% had good knowledge on diabetes in the communities.

The total awareness of diabetes risk factors was 75.0% amongst the respondents (Table 2). Family history (66.7%) and obesity (58.3%) were identified as the most common risk factors; while other risk factors include poor diet (50.0%), alcohol consumption (41.7%), smoking (37.5%), and lack of physical exercise (33.3%). Knowledge about hypertension (29.2%) and being older than 45 years (25.0%) was not high. About 4.2% believed diabetes could be caused by witchcraft, suggesting little reliance on non-medical causes for diabetes.

According to Table 3, polyuria was the most common symptom associated with diabetes among 66.7% of the participants, followed by excessive thirst (62.5%), fatigue

(58.3%), weight loss (50.0%), blurred vision (41.7%), delayed wound healing (33.3%), skin infection or itching (25.0%), and other symptoms (8.3%). The highest awareness rate concerning diabetes was in Emekuku.

In the case of Table 4, the main preventive methods mentioned by the respondents include exercise (75.0%) and having a healthy diet (70.8%). Weight management (66.7%) and cutting down on the intake of sugars and fats (62.5%) also emerged as popular choices. In terms of treatment options, awareness was highest for oral drugs (50.0%), followed by diet only treatment (41.7%) and insulin (33.3%). The means of getting their medications were through purchase for 66.7% of the respondents; however, some access to free medication was available in certain communities.

In Table 5, the majority of the respondents (83.3%) had heard that diabetes can cause other complications. Heart disease (70.8%), kidney damage (66.7%), vision problems (62.5%), and hypertension (58.3%) ranked among the most well-known complications. For the diabetic respondents, 66.6% had one or two complications, while 33.3% had more than three complications. Complications such as neuropathy (22.2%), nephropathy (16.7%), and foot ulcers (13.9%) were the ones most experienced by the respondents.

In terms of awareness of complications (Table 6), high levels of awareness were recorded in relation to vision loss (83.3%), kidney failure (81.7%), heart disease (79.2%), poor wound healing (78.3%), nerve damage (76.7%), amputation (73.3%), and stroke (70.8%). However, low awareness were reported in sexual dysfunction (41.7%) and dental problems (37.5%), indicating gaps in knowledge regarding less commonly discussed complications.

Table 1: Awareness and Knowledge of Diabetes among the study respondents

Item	Overall N = 1,200	OWERRI WEST			OWERRI NORTH		
		Okuku N = 200	Ndegwu N = 200	Amakohia- Ubi N = 200	Emii N = 200	Obibi- Ezena N = 200	Emekuku N = 200
Diagnosed with diabetes?							
Yes	180(15.0)	30(15.0)	33(16.5)	27(13.5)	33(16.5)	36(18.0)	21(10.5)
No	1,020(85.0)	170(85.0)	167(83.5)	173(86.5)	167(83.5)	164(82.0)	179(89.5)
If yes, what type of diabetes?							
Type-1	30(16.7)	4(13.3)	4(12.1)	7(25.9)	5(15.2)	6(16.7)	4(19.0)
Type-2	120(66.7)	21(70.0)	23(69.7)	15(55.6)	25(75.8)	23(63.9)	13(61.9)
Don't know	20(11.1)	4(13.3)	4(12.1)	4(14.8)	1(3.0)	5(13.9)	2(9.5)
Others	10(5.5)	1(3.3)	2(6.1)	1(3.7)	2(6.1)	2(5.6)	2(9.5)
Duration of diabetes							
<1 year	40(22.2)	7(23.3)	7(21.2)	8(29.6)	8(24.2)	6(16.7)	4(19.0)
1-5 years	80(44.4)	11(36.7)	14(42.4)	12(44.4)	14(14.4)	16(44.4)	13(61.9)
6-10 years	40(22.2)	8(26.7)	7(21.2)	5(18.5)	8(24.2)	10(27.8)	2(9.5)
>10 years	20(11.1)	4(13.3)	5(15.2)	2(7.4)	3(9.1)	4(11.1)	2(9.5)

Diabetes knowledge level							
Poor	500(41.7)	85(42.5)	80(40.0)	86(43.0)	83(41.5)	86(43.0)	80(40.0)
Fair	400(33.3)	64(32.0)	70(35.0)	62(31.0)	65(32.5)	68(34.0)	71(35.5)
Good	300(25.0)	51(25.5)	50(25.0)	52(26.0)	52(26.0)	46(23.0)	49(24.5)

Table 2: Awareness and Knowledge of Diabetes Risk Factors among the study respondents (multiple choice)

Item	Overall N = 1,200	OWERRI WEST			OWERRI NORTH		
		Okuku N = 200	Ndegwu N = 200	Amakohia- Ubi N = 200	Emii N = 200	Obibi- Ezena N = 200	Emekuku N = 200
Aware of risk factors?							
Yes	900(75.0)	162(81.0)	159(79.5)	167(83.5)	170(85.0)	166(83.0)	173(86.5)
No	300(25.0)	38(19.0)	41(19.5)	33(16.5)	30(15.0)	34(17.0)	27(13.5)
Known risk factors? (multiple choice)							
Family history	800(66.7)	130(65.0)	142(71.0)	135(67.5)	136(68.0)	115(57.5)	142(71.0)
Obesity	700(58.3)	109(54.5)	116(58.0)	121(60.5)	114(57.0)	118(59.0)	122(61.0)
Poor diet	600(50.0)	98(49.0)	88(44.0)	117(58.5)	111(55.5)	63(31.5)	120(60.0)
Alcohol	500(41.7)	65(32.5)	79(39.5)	69(34.5)	81(40.5)	91(45.5)	115(57.5)
Smoking	450(37.5)	65(32.5)	77(38.5)	59(29.5)	74(37.0)	80(40.0)	95(47.5)
Low physical activity	400(33.3)	68(34.0)	49(24.5)	52(26.0)	55(27.5)	76(38.0)	100(50.0)
Hypertension	350(29.2)	41(20.5)	41(20.5)	51(25.5)	49(24.5)	76(38.0)	92(46.0)
Age >45 years	300(25.0)	32(16.0)	38(19.0)	47(23.5)	49(24.5)	68(34.0)	66(33.0)
Witchcraft	50(4.2)	12(6.0)	7(3.5)	9(4.5)	9(4.5)	10(5.0)	3(1.5)

Table 3: Awareness and Knowledge of Diabetes Symptoms of diabetes among the study respondents (multiple choice)

Item	Overall N = 1,200	OWERRI WEST			OWERRI NORTH		
		Okuku N = 200	Ndegwu N = 200	Amakohia- Ubi N = 200	Emii N = 200	Obibi-Ezena N = 200	Emekuku N = 200
Frequent urination	800(66.7)	145 (72.5)	125 (62.5)	130 (65.0)	110 (55.0)	140 (70.0)	150 (75.0)
Excessive thirst	750(62.5)	130 (65.0)	115 (57.5)	120 (60.0)	125 (62.5)	135(67.5)	125(75.0)
Weight loss	600(50.0)	90(45.0)	110(55.0)	85(42.5)	95(47.5)	110(55.0)	110(55.0)
Blurred vision	500(41.7)	75(37.5)	90(45.0)	70(35.0)	85(42.5)	90(45.0)	90(45.0)
Slow-healing wounds	400(33.3)	65(32.5)	60(30.0)	75(37.5)	70(35.0)	65(32.5)	65(32.5)
Skin infection/itching	300(25.0)	50(25.0)	45(22.5)	55(27.5)	40(20.0)	55(27.5)	55(27.5)
Fatigue	700(58.3)	110(55.0)	120(60.0)	115(57.5)	105(52.5)	125(62.5)	125(62.5)
Others	100(8.3)	20(10.0)	15(7.5)	10(5.0)	15(7.5)	20(10.0)	20(10.0)

Table 4: Awareness and Knowledge of Diabetes Preventive methods and Treatment among the study respondents

Item	Overall N = 1,200	OWERRI WEST			OWERRI NORTH		
		Okuku N = 200	Ndegwu N = 200	Amakohia-Ubi N = 200	Emii N = 200	Obibi-Ezena N = 200	Emekuku N = 200
Known preventive methods (multiple choice)							
Exercise regularly	900(75.0)	150(75.0)	140(70.0)	145(72.5)	130(65.0)	120(60.0)	115(57.5)
Healthy diet	850(70.8)	140(70.0)	130(65.0)	140(70.0)	135(67.5)	130(65.0)	75(37.5)
Weight control	800(66.7)	130(65.0)	125(62.5)	140(70.0)	130(65.0)	95(47.5)	80(40.0)
Avoid alcohol	700(58.3)	120(60.0)	110(55.0)	115(57.5)	115(57.5)	110(55.0)	130(65.0)
Avoid smoking	680(56.7)	110(55.0)	115(57.5)	120(60.0)	115(57.5)	95(47.5)	125(62.5)
Reduce sugar/fat intake	750(62.5)	130(65.0)	120(60.0)	130(65.0)	120(60.0)	110(55.0)	140(70.0)
Diabetes treatment knowledge (multiple choice)							
Diet only	500(41.7)	90(45.0)	80(40.0)	85(42.5)	70(35.0)	90(45.0)	85(42.5)
Oral drugs	600(50.0)	100(50.0)	105(52.5)	110(55.0)	90(45.0)	95(47.5)	100(50.0)
Insulin intake	400(33.3)	70(35.0)	80(40.0)	50(25.0)	65(32.5)	65(32.5)	70(35.0)
Combined therapy	300(25.0)	50(25.0)	55(27.5)	60(30.0)	40(20.0)	45(22.5)	50(25.0)
Not sure	200(16.7)	30(15.0)	35(17.5)	40(20.0)	20(10.0)	35(17.5)	40(20.0)
Medication source (applied to respondents who answered "Yes")							
Purchased	120(66.7)	25(12.5)	20(10.0)	20(10.0)	15(7.5)	20(10.0)	40(20.0)
Free	60(33.3)	15(7.5)	15(7.5)	15(7.5)	10(5.0)	5(2.5)	0(0.0)

Table 5: Complications and Clinical Conditions

Item	Overall N = 1,200 (%)	OWERRI WEST (%)			OWERRI NORTH (%)		
		Okuku N = 200	Ndegwu N = 200	Amakohia-Ubi N = 200	Emii N = 200	Obibi-Ezena N = 200	Emekuku N = 200
Are you aware that diabetes can lead to complications?							
Yes	1,000(83.3)	170 (85.0)	162 (81.0)	165 (82.5)	166 (83.0)	169 (84.5)	168 (84.0)
No	200(16.7)	30 (15.0)	38 (19.0)	35 (17.5)	34 (17.0)	31 (15.5)	32 (16.0)
What complications are you aware of? (multiple choice)							
Heart disease	850(70.8)	148 (74.0)	134 (67.0)	138 (69.0)	144 (72.0)	142 (71.0)	144 (72.0)
Kidney damage	800(66.7)	130 (65.0)	129 (64.5)	136 (68.0)	132 (66.0)	136 (68.0)	137 (68.5)
Vision loss	750(62.5)	124 (62.0)	120 (60.0)	128 (64.0)	124 (62.0)	127 (63.5)	127 (63.5)
Foot ulcers	600(50.0)	96 (48.0)	98 (49.0)	102 (51.0)	94 (47.0)	105 (52.5)	105 (52.5)
hypertension	700(58.3)	112 (56.0)	114 (57.0)	120 (60.0)	117 (58.5)	119 (59.5)	118 (59.0)
Nerve damage	650(54.2)	108 (54.0)	107 (53.5)	110 (55.0)	106 (53.0)	111 (55.5)	108 (54.0)
Sexual dysfunction	300(25.0)	49 (24.5)	50 (25.0)	52 (26.0)	47 (23.5)	51 (25.5)	51 (25.5)

Amputation	500(41.7)	81 (40.5)	83 (41.5)	85 (42.5)	80 (40.0)	86 (43.0)	85 (42.5)
None	100(55.6)	12 (6.0)	10 (5.0)	11 (5.5)	11 (5.5)	9 (4.5)	10 (5.0)
If diabetic, how many complications do you currently have? (among diabetics, n=180)							
1-2 complications	120(66.6)	21 (70.0)	18 (60.0%)	19 (63.3)	20 (66.7)	21 (70.0)	21 (70.0)
More than 3	60(33.3)	9 (30.0)	12 (40.0%)	11 (36.7)	10 (33.3)	9 (30.0)	9 (30.0)
Which specific complications have you experienced?							
Neuropathy	40(22.2)	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)
Nephropathy	30(16.7)	6 (20.0)	5 (16.7)	4 (13.3)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)
Retinopathy	20(11.1)	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)
Foot ulcer	25(13.9)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	4 (13.3)	4 (13.3)
Others	15(8.3)	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	3 (10.0)

Table 6: Overall Perceptions of Respondents about Diabetes-related complications

Complications	Yes (%)	No (%)
Stroke	850(70.8)	350(29.2)
Heart disease	950(79.2)	250(20.8)
Vision loss	1000(83.3)	200(16.7)
Kidney failure	980(81.7)	220(18.3)
Nerve damage	920(76.7)	280(23.3)
Sexual dysfunction	500(41.7)	700(58.3)
Amputation	880(73.3)	320(26.7)
Poor wound healing	940(78.3)	260(21.7)
Dental issues	450(37.5)	750(62.5)

DISCUSSION:

The results obtained from Table 1 contribute valuable information concerning the rate of diabetes prevalence, diabetes awareness, and patients' knowledge concerning their condition. The prevalence rate of 15% found in this research exceeds considerably the prevalence rate in the whole country previously established in Nigeria. For instance, according to Uloko *et al.* (2018), the prevalence rate in the country was 5.77%. Prevalence rates of other studies conducted in Lagos, Edo, and Oyo States were in the range of 4%-6% (Olamoyegun *et al.*, 2024; Ehwarime *et al.*, 2018; Adejoh, 2014). It seems that diabetes is becoming increasingly prevalent or that its identification becomes more successful due to increased awareness. Type-2 diabetes was diagnosed as one of the most common forms of this disease since it comprised 66.7% of cases; however, this statistic corresponds to data worldwide as well as in Nigeria, where Type-2 diabetes predominates among adults (Iregbu *et al.*, 2022). Nevertheless, it represents only 90% globally while

11.1% of people did not know about their diabetes types. Moreover, the majority of participants had been living with the condition for 1-5 years, implying better awareness and early diagnosis than seen in previous research conducted in Enugu and Imo States, where there was a prevalence of delays in diagnosis and complications arising from the condition (Asonye and Ojewole, 2023; Mgbahurike *et al.*, 2017). In terms of knowledge, the findings revealed that 41.7% had poor knowledge, 33.3% fair knowledge, while only 25.0% had good knowledge. Though this represents moderate knowledge compared to previous studies done in rural Nigeria (Aikabeli *et al.*, 2025; Amadi *et al.*, 2019), the level of poor knowledge is concerning.

Results from Table 2 showed a general level of high awareness on diabetes risk factors among the respondents. In total, 75.0% of the participants reported one form of diabetes risk factor. The most common risk factors recognized included family history, obesity, poor eating habits, drinking alcohol, smoking, and lack of physical

activity. This finding is consistent with previous research by the International Diabetes Federation (2021) and studies done in Ekiti and Anambra States where heredity, obesity, and unhealthy lifestyle behaviors were established as major causes of Type-2 diabetes mellitus (Richard *et al.*, 2021; Okoronkwo *et al.*, 2019). Emekuku maintained the highest level of awareness, which shows that there was higher exposure to healthcare knowledge and interventions in this community. Low physical activities, high blood pressure, and old age had lower awareness levels compared to other risk factors, consistent with the study by Uloko *et al.* (2018), indicating that many Nigerians lack adequate knowledge about cardiovascular and lifestyle-based diabetes risk factors. Notably, a low number of respondents linked witchcraft with diabetes.

Awareness of signs and symptoms of diabetes was moderately to highly prevalent in the study communities, as per the results obtained from Table 3. Frequent urination, intense thirst, and tiredness were some of the most commonly recognized signs of diabetes, consistent with previous literature, in which such classical signs of diabetes were reported to be commonly detected by respondents (World Health Organization, 2023; Olamoyegun *et al.*, 2024; Aikabeli *et al.*, 2025). Awareness of weight loss was similarly quite common among respondents. Nonetheless, knowledge of other symptoms, such as blurred vision, poor wound healing, and skin infection, was rather low. Uloko *et al.* (2018) found a similar lack of knowledge about less common symptoms of diabetes in Nigerians.

The results found in table 4 indicated that there is high awareness of methods used in the prevention and treatment of diabetes among the respondents. Majority of the respondents mentioned regular physical activities, healthy diet, maintaining a healthy body weight, and eating low amounts of sugars and fats as some of the preventive measures against diabetes. These results have a correlation with other researches done in urban areas in Nigeria where public health programs emphasized the adoption of a healthy lifestyle as an important measure of disease prevention (Otaniyenuwa and Andrew, 2021). Results also revealed that knowledge of treatment methods is average since only half of the respondents indicated the use of oral medication in diabetes management. Other treatment measures which include insulin treatment and combined treatment were not mentioned by many of the respondents. Dieting alone was suggested by a few respondents as an effective treatment method for diabetes. Limited awareness of treatment measures and treatment protocols had also been found to be common in the cities of Kano and Port Harcourt.

The findings presented in Table 5 indicated a high level of awareness regarding diabetes-related complications, with 83.3% of respondents being aware that diabetes

might cause serious medical issues. The complications mentioned most frequently by the participants were heart disease, kidney complications, and blindness, which corroborates findings from previous studies carried out in Nigeria and Ethiopia, where diabetic patients suffered from nephropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular conditions (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2016; Gebremedhin *et al.*, 2019). Sexual dysfunction and amputations were less recognized by the surveyed population, similar to other studies in Saudi Arabia and Africa, where stigma and limited health knowledge prevent patients from knowing about such complications (Al-Rubeaan *et al.*, 2023). Complications such as neuropathy, nephropathy, and foot ulcers were among the most commonly mentioned in responses from diabetic individuals. Nevertheless, a lower percentage of participants faced those complications in comparison with previous hospital-based studies due to differences in patient characteristics. Lastly, the results from Table 6 showed very high levels of awareness about the major complications of diabetes such as blindness, kidney problems, heart conditions, poor wound healing, nerve problems, strokes, and amputations. The results were consistent with previous research findings that had shown very high levels of awareness in states like Imo State, Kaduna State, and South Africa due to greater exposure to health care services and education on diabetes (Onyenekwe *et al.*, 2021; Mash *et al.*, 2015). The respondents were generally not aware of dental issues and sexual dysfunctions. In summary, the results obtained from the study show that there is need to improve the awareness of diabetes complications in rural communities in Imo State. Nonetheless, there were still gaps in the areas of different types, symptoms, treatments, and some diabetes complications.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study show that there was a relatively higher prevalence of diabetes amongst the rural inhabitants of Owerri West and Owerri North Local Government Areas of Imo State, with type 2 diabetes accounting for the highest number of cases. Though the respondents exhibited moderate to a high level of awareness concerning the risk factors, symptoms, prevention measures, and possible complications associated with diabetes, there was significant lack of awareness as regards the types of diabetes, modes of treatment and the lesser-known complications such as sexual impotence and dental problems. It was established that risk factors like family history of diabetes, obesity, poor dietary practices and unhealthy life style were well known by the respondents, while physical exercises and a balanced diet were known as preventive measures. Similarly, there was a high level of awareness about major

complications like cardiovascular diseases, kidney failure, and blindness.

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